

Verification of precipitation forecasts simulated by ALADIN and AROME over Algeria

Islam BOUSRI¹, Mohamed MOKHTARI¹

⁽¹⁾ Numerical Weather Prediction Department, Office Nationale de la Météorologie, Algiers, ALGERIA.

Abstract

Precipitation forecasts have always been of great interest to forecasters because they influence daily life. In this paper we present the first results of verification of precipitation simulated by ALADIN and AROME over Algeria using a contingency table approach. The main synoptic messages over the whole domain of ALADIN-Algérie has been used as reference.

A fuzzy theory is applied to compare the forecasts with a specific perimeter, thus allowing to take into account the spatial variability of precipitation in a more accurate way. This allows the performance of precipitation forecasting models to be evaluated in terms of detection probability, false alarm rate, precision and accuracy.

Examples of results obtained during September to December of 2022 period are presented, highlighting the evolution of precipitation forecast model performance over time. These results provide important informations on the ability of ALADIN and AROME operational models to predict precipitation in Algeria and give the identification of the strengths and weaknesses of these two models.

1 Introduction

Precipitation is a discrete variable with stochastic behaviour that on small scales presents fractal properties. For these reasons, it is difficult to simulate and verify. Several precipitation verification methods have been developed. The contingency tables was one of these method and they were entered the field of forecast verification more then one hundred years ago and they continue to be an area of intensive research. The reason is the ability of contingency table to condense and clearly display the properties of some set of forecasts and corresponding observations. Utilization of contingency tables is particularly useful for the verification of quantitative precipitation forecasts, which is for many reasons difficult to verify.

For example, Gold et al. (2019) used a contingency table to verify the performance of probabilistic rain and lightning forecasts and determine necessary adjustments using an established verification process. Baig et al (2023) made a study to examine the consistency and applicability of four satellite precipitation products, namely PERSIANN, PERSIANN-CCS, PERSIANN-CDR and PDIR-Now, over the UAE using the contingency table. Giarno et al. (2018) evaluated the accuracy of satellite precipitation estimates in regions with large variations in rainfall patterns. Montesarchio et al. (2015) compared different precipitation threshold estimates using empirical data, hydrological simulations, and probabilistic methods, and evaluated system performance using contingency tables.

The purpose of this paper is to explore the use of the contingency table as a statistical tool to verify the precipitations simulated by the operational numerical weather prediction models ALADIN and AROME over Algeria. We will present the basic principles of the contingency table and explain how it can be used to evaluate the performance of precipitation forecasting models. We will also discuss the benefits of this approach, emphasizing its relevance for forecast validation and continuous improvement of numerical models.

In addition, we will emphasize the importance of taking into account the different precipitation thresholds in the analysis of model performance. The contingency table is used to quantify forecast errors, identify systematic patterns of under- or over-forecasting, and evaluate the ability of models to capture extreme precipitation events.

We also show an example of verification results obtained during September to December, 2022 period. These results were compared against ARPEGE.

2 Data and methods

2.1 Data

The observations used in our study were extracted from the main SYNOP messages, specifically from section 1 of group 6RRRtR. Since this group is coded differently according to each National Meteorological and Hydrological Services as shown in the Table 1, we have perform arithmetic operations to obtain a cumulative precipitation over a 6-hour period, which is the frequency used in this study to evaluate our models.

The verification domains for ALADIN and AROME and the observation sites used are shown in figure 1.

Table 1: Coding of group 6 in SYNOP .

	Europe	Algeria & Morocco	Tunisia
0600 Z	tR=2 Rainfall totals accumulated 12h	tR=4 Rainfall totals accumulated 24h	tR=4 Rainfall totals accumulated 24h
1200 Z	tR=1 Rainfall totals accumulated 6h	tR=1 Rainfall totals accumulated 6h	tR=1 Rainfall totals accumulated 6h
1800 Z	tR=2 Rainfall totals accumulated 12h	tR=2 Rainfall totals accumulated 12h	tR=2 Rainfall totals accumulated 12h
0000 Z	tR=1 Rainfall totals accumulated 6h	tR=1 Rainfall totals accumulated 6h	tR=3 Rainfall totals accumulated 18h

Figure 1 :Observations used for model checking.

2.2 Methods:

A contingency table is a table that summarizes the results of a classification based on two variables.

In meteorology, a contingency table can be used to compare weather forecasts to actual observations. It is often used to evaluate the quality of weather forecasts and to calculate performance measures such as accuracy, false positive rate and false negative rate.

Table 2 : Example of a contingency table for comparing rain forecasts with observations.

	Positive Observations	Negative Observations
Positive Forecast	True positive (TP)	False positive (FP)
Negative Forecast	False negative (FN)	True negative (TN)

In this table, positive forecasts indicate that rain was forecast, while negative forecasts indicate that rain was not forecast. Positive observations indicate that rain was observed, while negative observations indicate that no rain was observed. The TP, FP, FN, and TN values represent the numbers of true positive, false positive, false negative, and true negative results, respectively.

From this contingency table, performance measures can be calculated, such as:

$$\text{- False alarm rate (FAR)} = \frac{FP}{(FP+TP)} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{- Probability of detection (POD)} = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)} \tag{2}$$

$$\text{- Precision} = \frac{TP}{(TP+FP)} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{- Accuracy} = \frac{(TP+TN)}{(TP+FP+TP+TN)} \tag{4}$$

These measurements allow us to evaluate the quality of rain forecasts in comparison with real observations in several thresholds of rainfall (0.2mm , 0.5mm , 1mm , 5mm , 10mm , 20mm).

When high-resolution forecasts from numerical models are evaluated using traditional measurements, they often show poor results due to difficulties in obtaining an exact match with high-resolution observations. In this study, we propose to use a "fuzzy" verification approach (Ebert, 2008) that relies on the use of a spatial window or neighborhood surrounding the forecast points over a radius of 50km . This fuzzy approach better accounts for spatial variability and overcomes the limitations of traditional measurements in the evaluation of high-resolution numerical model forecasts.

Figure 2 : Single observation neighborhood forecast.

3 Results

In this section, we will present some examples of the results obtained, highlighting the contingency tables and the evolution of several metrics such as detection probability, false alarm rate, precision and accuracy. Figure 3 shows verification scores of six-hour accumulated precipitations simulated by ALADIN and AROME for 0.2mm, 5mm and 20mm threshold values. These scores are compared with ARPEGE.

While the metrics are almost similar between ALADIN and ARPEGE, AROME stands out with better accuracy and precision for the 0.2 mm threshold and then joins the other models for the 5 mm threshold.

Figure 3 : Contingency table of six-hour accumulated precipitations simulated by ALADIN and AROME for 0.2mm, 5mm and 20mm threshold values.

Figure 4 shows the evolution by threshold of the probability of detection, false alarm rate, precision and accuracy for six-hour accumulated precipitations.

This graph provides the same information as the contingency tables in the previous figure, but with more details. It confirms the similar behaviour between ARPEGE and ALADIN, while highlighting the favourable performance scores for AROME for thresholds below 5 mm.

Figure 4 : Evolution by threshold of the probability of detection, false alarm rate, precision and accuracy for six-hour accumulated precipitations.

In figure 5 we will see the evolution by forecast time of the probability of detection, the false alarm rate, the precision and the accuracy .

No significant trend is observed in the evolution of the scores, indicating a stable behaviour where the models produce almost similar results for the different metrics.

Figure 5 : Evolution of the probability of detection, the false alarm rate, the precision and the accuracy.

Figure 6 shows the monthly evolution of the probability of detection, false-alarm, precision and accuracy for six-hour accumulated precipitations. What is particularly notable in this figure is that all of the scores (POD, FAR, Precision and accuracy) show a very pronounced peak in the month of November. This result makes sense, as that month was characterized by a period of heavy rainfall.

Figure 6 : Monthly evolution of the probability of detection, false-alarm, precision and accuracy for six-hour accumulated precipitations.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents the first results of verification of six-hour accumulated precipitation simulated by ALADIN and AROME over Algeria against observation using a contingency table approach. The results obtained over September to December of 2022 period showed interesting trends, highlighting the improvement of model accuracy over time.

Programs developed in this work will be deployed in operational to progress our verification chain already in place for surface parameters (temperature, wind, humidity and pressure).

However, improvement perspectives remain to be explored. Among them, it would be relevant to introduce other extreme parameters such as wind gusts, in order to better understand the behaviour of our models such AROME.

5 References

Baig, F., Abrar, M., Chen, H., & Sherif, M. (2023), Evaluation of Precipitation Estimates from Remote Sensing and Artificial Neural Network Based Products (PERSIANN) Family in an Arid Region. *Remote Sensing*, 15(4), 1078. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15041078>.

Ebert, E. E. (2008), Fuzzy verification of high-resolution gridded forecasts : a review and proposed framework. *Meteorological Applications*, 15(1), 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.25>.

Giarno, G., Hadi, M. N. S., Suprayogi, S., & Murti, S. H. (2018), Distribution of Accuracy of TRMM Daily Rainfall in Makassar Strait. *Forum Geografi*, 32(1), 38-52. <https://doi.org/10.23917/forgeo.v32i1.5774>.

Gold, S., White, E. B., Roeder, W. P., McAleenan, M., Schubert, C. M., & Ahner, D. K. (2019), Probabilistic Contingency Tables : An Improvement to Verify Probability Forecasts. *Weather and Forecasting*, 35(2), 609-621. <https://doi.org/10.1175/waf-d-19-0116.1>.

Montesarchio, V., Napolitano, F., Rianna, M., Ridolfi, E., Russo, F., & Sebastianelli, S. (2015), Comparison of methodologies for flood rainfall thresholds estimation. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-014-1357-3>.